

A Farmer-Led Approach to Landscape Recovery

Review, Assessment, and Next Steps

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

What does a farmer-centred approach to landscape recovery look like? How can collaborative efforts for landscape recovery be fostered to support applications for the Landscape Recovery Scheme (LRS)?

This report explores the above questions through a FiPL-funded project designed to empower land managers as key drivers of environmental change. The findings presented in this executive summary are based on a comprehensive analysis of the process – its structure, outputs, outcomes, and the firsthand experiences of those involved. They are intended to support participating land managers, as well as those with an interest in collaborative landscape recovery within and in proximity of the Dark Peak, in devising future plans for collaboration.

Motivations for taking part

- The project is seen as a crucial first step toward large-scale collaboration for nature recovery and climate resilience, including schemes like LRS.
- Access to subsidised, large-scale efforts is vital for sustaining sheep farming businesses.
- Land managers seek greater control over the delivery of environmental objectives.
- The project, as well as the higher-tier LRS, are viewed as an opportunity for land managers to regain control and ensure the long-term sustainability of hill farming.
- A results-based approach to environmental land management is favoured over its action-based counterpart for its less prescriptive character and potential to give land managers greater control over landscape management.

The structure of a farmer-centred approach for landscape recovery

- Land managers praised the work of the consultant and emphasised the importance of involving someone they know and trust in the project's facilitation.
- Farm plans were valued for their clarity, conciseness, and accuracy.
- The *Farmer Checklist* was useful and praised for its accessibility, but under-utilised.
- Final group meeting and presentations were well-received by land managers.

Several suggestions were nevertheless made for land managers who might wish to adopt a farmer-centred approach that can successfully prepare them for the development of a LRS application:

- Allocate time for a dedicated meeting among land managers and the consultant to explore landscape-scale opportunities.
- Incorporate land manager visits to other land managers' farms to observe practices and raise ambition.
- Conduct the project in a season more suitable for on-site exploration.
- Better prepare for collaboration at the project's outset (e.g. reviewing best practices across participating holdings, farm visits, and dedicated discussion days).
- Ensure all land managers attend and allow plenty of time for stakeholder discussions.
- Address ambiguity in task allocation and responsibilities from the beginning.

The vision's ambition

- Many land managers feel they are already implementing significant measures for nature recovery and climate resilience.
- Some expressed caution against assumptions favouring no intervention or no grazing due to risks like wildfires.

- They broadly acknowledged that changes in land management practices are necessary, particularly for the development of a LRS application.
- Willingness to adopt new practices (e.g. introducing cattle grazing) varied among participating land managers.

Some suggestions were made to make sure future initiatives of this kind are more closely aligned with LRS expectations:

- Successful practices on one holding could serve as a model for others.
- Stakeholders emphasised the need for ambitious targets and demonstrable commitment to change for LRS success.
- Adjustments to grazing patterns may be necessary to support species like waders.
- Collaborative planning and sharing strategies among land managers could enhance effectiveness in achieving LRS goals.

Insights specific to a potential LRS application in the Dark Peak were also provided. Those include the following:

- The core and distinctive landscape in the Dark Peak is peatland.
- A suggestion was made to make peatland restoration a centrepiece of the application.
- Land managers might consider meeting a range of collaboratively identified outcomes after 25 years, such as a demonstrable commitment to rewet moorland areas or a demonstrable commitment to bold woodland creation where trees do not have to compete with peat.
- How land managers achieve those outcomes will be their responsibility, but a demonstrable commitment to such outcomes will be key to securing a successful a LRS application.
- Meeting those outcomes might require changes in grazing patterns or enforcing predator control but deciding how they are met will be the focus of farmer-led collaboration.

The next steps

- Project seen as a valuable opportunity to test approaches, gather insights, and refine methods for future use.
- Recognised as a "valuable first step" in planning for participating land managers' holdings.
- Land managers eager to build on project momentum and identify short- and medium-term collaboration opportunities.
- Proposal to resume discussions in May/June 2026 to maintain progress.
- Immediate next step: Prioritise areas for potential collaboration like cross-holding woodland creation.
- Shared optimism about the project's outcomes, with opportunities identified that don't require waiting for LRS application.
- Potential for short- and medium-term actions to be pursued independently.
- Suggested development of a collaborative, landscape-scale payment-by-result initiative.

2. INTRODUCTION

Peakland Environmental Farmers (PEF) is a cooperative of farmers and moorland managers, collectively responsible for the stewardship of over 45,800 hectares across the Dark Peak and Southwest Peak. PEF's mission is to deliver large-scale environmental outcomes – including nature recovery, climate mitigation, and improved water quality – while securing fair financial returns for sustainable farming and game management through collaboration.

This project, led by PEF members managing 11,777 hectares and funded by Farming in Protected Landscapes (FiPL), builds upon the group's previous heritage and conservation work.

Project Scope and Vision

The project aims to engage key stakeholders – including landowners, farming tenants, and sporting interests – in developing a farmer-led vision for landscape recovery. This vision is supported by statutory and voluntary conservation partners and aligns with national and local environmental frameworks, such as the Environmental Improvement Plan, the Peak District National Park Management Plan, Local Nature Recovery Strategies, and the '30 by 30' biodiversity target. Where applicable, the project directly addresses objectives for Sites of Special Scientific Interest (SSSI), Special Areas of Conservation (SAC), and Special Protection Areas (SPA).

Through targeted farmer engagement, strategic partnerships, and early-stage conservation planning, the project seeks to establish a foundation for long-term environmental delivery. It also initiates research and development to position PEF for access to environmental markets, alternative funding streams, and coordinated agri-environment schemes, facilitating a transition from the Basic Payment Scheme to more sustainable and rewarding land management models.

Aims and objectives

The project's primary aim is to support farmers in developing a landscape-scale, farmer-centred vision for environmental recovery within a protected landscape.

The project will deliver a concise, collaborative vision for a landscape area containing nationally protected sites, supported by statutory and landowning partners, and aligned with government targets for environmental protection, nature recovery, and climate change adaptation and mitigation. This preparatory exercise is designed to inform future Landscape Recovery schemes and private financing opportunities.

Expected outcomes

This project aims to lay the groundwork for a locally-led, financially viable, farmer-led approach to landscape recovery. It seeks to unlock large-scale environmental improvements, contribute meaningfully to national and local targets, and provide new income streams for local farmers and moorland managers in the Peak District. The lessons learned and the vision developed will be shared with the broader PEF group and other farmer clusters, positioning this work as a demonstrator for farmer-led landscape recovery across the region and beyond.

Participants in the Process

The project involved a diverse range of stakeholders, each contributing at different stages:

- **Nine participating land managers** – These included sheep farmers and grouse moor managers engaged through farm visits and stakeholder meetings.

- **PEF co-director** – Responsible for coordinating workstreams and organising stakeholder meetings.
- **Farm and environment consultant** – Involved throughout the process, excluding one-to-one interviews.
- **Members of local environmental non-governmental organisations (ENGOS) and arms-length bodies** – Participated in stakeholder meetings.
- **Game & Wildlife Conservation Trust (GWCT)** – Served on the steering group and aggregated individual farm plans.
- **Social scientist** – Supported the consultant and collected data for the report through observations and interviews.

The social science work

Given the experimental nature of the initiative and its aim to foster landscape-scale collaboration in the Peak District and surrounding areas, it was essential to thoroughly document its structure, outputs, and outcomes, as well as the diverse experiences of most participants involved in the process. A social scientist was commissioned to analyse these aspects, and this report synthesises their findings alongside insights drawn from several key activities. The overarching aims of this social scientific work were:

- To examine what a farmer-centred approach to landscape recovery in the Dark Peak might look like.
- To understand how collaborative efforts for landscape recovery can be fostered to support applications for the Landscape Recovery Scheme (LRS).

The analysis presented in this report is based on direct observations of the farmer-centred process, including group meetings and a selection of farm visits. It also incorporates a detailed review of the *Farmer Checklist* and *Individual Farm Plans*, which provided valuable data on participant engagement and progress. Additionally, exit interviews were conducted with the majority of participating land managers and stakeholders, offering further depth to the findings.

In total, seven of the nine land managers participated in interviews, along with representatives from two of the three stakeholder organisations. While the research aimed to be as comprehensive as possible, time constraints – both for the researcher and participants – meant that not all individuals could be interviewed.

The study adhered to rigorous ethical standards, receiving approval (application ID 11390932) from the University of Exeter. To ensure confidentiality, all participant names were replaced with pseudonyms, such as "Land Manager 1" and "Stakeholder 1." Identifying details, including specific locations and organizational names, were also anonymised to protect participant privacy. The fieldwork was supported by the NERC-funded RENEW project (NE/W004941/1).

3. THE PROCESS

The process leading to the formulation of a collective vision for landscape recovery involved the following stages:

- 3.1. Scoping/contextual analysis and start-of-process stakeholder meeting
- 3.2. Individual Farm Plans
- 3.3. End-of-process stakeholder meeting

3.1. Scoping/contextual analysis and start-of-process stakeholder meeting

The primary objective of this initial phase was to develop a concise and accessible guide – referred to as the ‘Farmer Checklist’ (see Appendix) – outlining key environmental and cultural/heritage targets for participating land managers. Recognising the time constraints faced by stakeholders, the document was designed to be clear, succinct, and directly applicable to their operational contexts.

Key targets identified through this review were aggregated into a summary table (see Appendix), which was subsequently shared with stakeholders in preparation for the November group meeting. Feedback received during this meeting informed revisions to the document, ensuring its relevance and clarity.

The farm and environment consultant led the creation of the *Farmer Checklist*. First, it involved a desk study review of key documents, where the goal of England environmental policy for improving nature, water, soil, and climate resilience are set. The documents include the Environmental Improvement Plan (2023 and 2025), the Peak District National Park Management Plan, the Protected Landscapes Targets and Outcomes Framework, and Local Nature Recovery Strategies from three key regional authorities for the Dark Peak (South Yorkshire, Derbyshire, West Yorkshire).

Key targets were aggregated in a table, which was shared with the stakeholders participating in the November group meeting. The meeting was aimed at introducing the project (its aims and structure), including the role of the social scientist as observer and analyst of the process. It also sought to ensure that parties participating in the process agreed on the expectations for the project, particularly in terms of nature recovery targets. However, participating land managers were not invited to this meeting, which mainly comprised the local stakeholders (NGOs and arms-length bodies), the PEF co-director, the farm and environmental consultant, and social scientist.

Local stakeholders placed a particularly strong emphasis on the importance of demonstrating land use change, e.g. how grazing is managed, for a Landscape Recovery Scheme application. Participating land managers were also encouraged to be bold and ambitious.

3.2. Individual farm plans

The objective of this phase was to develop bespoke environmental plans for each participating farm, ensuring that each document was tailored to the specific characteristics, history, and aspirations of the landholding in question. The resulting plans provide a comprehensive overview of each farm, incorporating detailed information on farm characteristics, the history of participation in agri-environment schemes, existing environmental assets, the stated aspirations of farmers and landowners, alignment with national, regional, and local environmental priorities and targets, and identified opportunities for environmental enhancement.

Methodology

Farm visits constituted the central component of this research phase, coordinated by a farm and environment consultant. Prior to each visit, land managers received the *Farmer Checklist* and were encouraged to review its contents in advance. A minimum of one on-site visit was scheduled per holding, typically conducted in an informal setting, such as around the kitchen table. In cases where farms had complex occupancy structures – such as those involving both tenants and landlords – additional visits were arranged to ensure comprehensive engagement. Follow-up visits or online meetings were also organised to discuss and finalise draft plans, securing approval from the relevant land managers.

During the farm visits, which ranged from three to six hours in duration, the consultant systematically reviewed each land parcel using LandApp, a digital mapping tool. This process involved documenting both the baseline delivery and the land managers' aspirations for each parcel, recorded in real time using LandApp's layer function. The consultant also maintained detailed notes to ensure all relevant information was captured.

A deliberate effort was made to centre the process around the land managers' perspectives. This involved reviewing each parcel and soliciting their input on potential actions. The consultant provided targeted suggestions – such as establishing clough woodland along streams – allowing land managers to either adopt or decline these recommendations based on their preferences and operational constraints.

To gain insights into the process, the social scientist participated in three farm visits: one with a landowner and two with sheep farmers. While it was neither feasible nor necessary to attend all visits, these observations provided a robust understanding of the key features and dynamics characterising this phase of the research. Visits were not recorded to foster an open and candid dialogue, allowing land managers to freely express their views on the issues discussed during the meetings.

Key observations

Influence of land manager identity: Land managers' aspirations were closely tied to their professional identities, whether as sheep farmers or grouse moor managers. The primary business activity of each holding significantly influenced their willingness to engage in specific land management practices.

Sheep farmers demonstrated reluctance to convert productive grazing land for nature recovery purposes, prioritizing parcels favoured by sheep for grazing. Grouse moor managers exhibited hesitation toward tree planting initiatives, citing concerns about attracting predators that could threaten grouse populations. Additionally, some land managers expressed scepticism regarding the efficacy of certain nature recovery interventions, such as using stone dams for gully blocking.

Tenant-landlord dynamics: differences in aspirations were also observed between tenants and landlords. These dynamics occasionally influenced the feasibility and scope of proposed land management actions.

3.3. End-of-process stakeholder meeting

The primary aim of the meeting was to convene all parties involved in the project, providing a platform for presenting land managers' aspirations, reflecting on their ambition, and identifying the next steps. Invited attendees included the majority of participating land managers,

representatives from local non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and arms-length bodies, the consultant facilitating the process, gamekeepers, the PEF co-director, and a representative of GWCT. The social scientist attended remotely via Microsoft Teams.

The PEF co-director opened the meeting with an introduction to the project, emphasising historical bones of contention between local stakeholders and land managers. This was followed by the presentation of the social scientist, who reiterated their role and outlined the next steps, including invitations for exit interviews.

The farm consultant then detailed the process of compiling individual farm plans and provided an overview of the aspirations for each holding. A GWCT representative subsequently offered insights into the broader implications of these aspirations, extrapolating their potential impact if adopted across the entire PEF membership. According to their calculations, the collective efforts of PEF members could potentially achieve most of the environmental targets relevant to the area. The meeting concluded with an open forum for questions and discussion.

Key observations

There was a strong emphasis by presenters and land managers themselves on the contributions the latter already make toward nature conservation. Land managers expressed a clear willingness to build on the momentum generated by the project. However, concerns were also raised by sheep farmers regarding the future viability of their businesses in the face of recent policy developments. Participating land managers were particularly vocal about the importance of protecting farming in the Peak District, both for their livelihoods and for local communities. They acknowledged the necessity of prioritising nature recovery and climate resilience, encapsulating their perspective with the statement by a land manager that “people matter just as much as the measurable benefits to nature.”

The meeting allocated minimal time for representatives of NGOs and arms-length bodies to share their perspectives on the process, vision, and responses to the claims and concerns raised during the presentations and discussions. Stakeholders did nevertheless recognise the enthusiasm of participating land managers and focused on identifying next steps. They reiterated the targets of particular interest to them, highlighting opportunities aligned with the aspirations outlined in the farm plans. A suggestion was made to identify common delivery themes across the different holdings and to leverage the unique opportunities for bold and ambitious nature recovery and climate resilience in the Dark Peak. The importance of collaboration and mutual learning was also emphasised. Additionally, stakeholders underscored the need to demonstrate land use changes for Landscape Recovery Scheme. It was clarified that environmental policies were never intended to undermine farming; rather, they aim to support and enhance sustainable agricultural practices.

4. LAND MANAGERS' VISION

This section reviews the environmental aspirations of the participating farmers, derived by aggregating the actions listed under the future delivery sections of each individual farm plan. Before examining those aspirations directly, it is both useful and important to establish a clear understanding of the land management practices already in place across the participating holdings.

This baseline context serves two purposes: it characterises the environmental work currently being undertaken across the farms, and it allows for a more informed assessment of the degree of change that farmers' aspirations would represent relative to their existing practices.

Both the baseline activity and future delivery sections are organised around a common set of categories, reflecting those used in the review of local, regional, and national targets. These categories are: habitat management, water, soil, and flood management, peatland restoration, climate and wildfire resilience, and species recovery.

Area size of priority habitats across the 9 holdings:

Table 1: Priority habitats

Priority habitat	Area size (ha)
Upland heathland	5145.5
Blanket bog	3577.5
Upland oak woodland	116.5
Purple moor grass and rush pasture	69.75
Upland flushes, fens and swamps	43
Wet heathland with cross-leaved heath, upland	35
Wood pasture and parkland	34
Lowland dry acid grassland	32
Lowland hay meadows	19.75
Lowland dry acid grassland	23.5
Lowland heathland	15
Good quality semi-improved grassland	15
Mixed scrub	2.5
Upland birch woodland	1.25
Scot's Pine woodland	1
Wet woodland	0.75

4.1. Baseline activity

Participating land managers already implement a range of actions aligned with the *Farmer Checklist's* environmental targets, reflecting ongoing efforts – whether through agri-environment schemes, SSSI/SAC/SPA regulations, or voluntary initiatives. Across the nine farms, key practices include:

Grazing controls dominant species like purple moor grass, enhances habitats for ground-nesting and wading birds, sustains soil health via low-intensity methods, and supports

conservation programmes like Higher-Level Stewardship (HLS). Peatland restoration protects biodiversity, stores carbon, improves water quality by curbing erosion and retaining water, and strengthens climate resilience through flood mitigation and carbon sequestration.

Reducing chemical use enhances water quality, while erosion control and moorland dams aid natural flood management. Herbal leys, low stocking rates, extensive grazing, and minimal machinery use collectively preserve soil health. Vegetation management, water retention, erosion control, carbon sequestration, and wildfire prevention help ecosystems adapt to climate extremes.

Predator control, targeted grazing, habitat creation, woodland establishment, and diverse habitats further drive species recovery, benefiting a wide array of bird populations.

Table 2 reviews the different baseline activities on participating land managers' holdings.

Table 2: Overview of baseline delivery

Habitat management	Water, soil, flood management	Peatland restoration	Climate and wildfire resilience	Species recovery
Low input grazing	Limiting or even eliminating the use of artificial fertilisers and pesticides	Reduce bare peat areas	Riparian woodlands cool streams, supporting cold-water species like salmonids	Legal predation control to promote wading bird populations
Seasonal livestock removal	Targeted farm manure when used	Actions to retain water, e.g. turf dams, and reduce erosion risk	In-field trees help mitigate climate impacts, providing forage and shelter during extreme weather	Grazing management to promote wading bird populations
Cattle grazing to tackle purple moor grass	Low stocking rates and minimal machinery use prevent soil erosion	Actions to stabilise peat or promote peat formation	Peatland works (turf/stone dams, revegetation) retain water, stabilize peat, reduce erosion risk, and promote carbon sequestration	Creation of scrapes and rush control also promote wading bird populations
Hay cutting after mid-July	In-bye wetland features to support waders during dry springs and enhance climate resilience		Wildfire risk management plan, e.g. firebreaks through heather cutting, less flammable vegetation near roads/tracks, water sources for firefighting	Clough woodland creation benefits woodland birds

Predator control to protect ground-nesting birds	Natural Flood Management: Install turf dams to store water on moorland, reducing flood risk downstream		Low stocking rates and peatland management enhance resilience to drought and heavy rainfall	Several actions taken, e.g. promoting diverse habitats, also benefit passerines and raptors
Control of invasive species	Herbal leys to improve soil structure			
Selective burning/cutting on shallow peat – no burning on deep peat	Low stocking rates and extensive grazing maintain good soil health			

4.2. Future delivery plans

Targets and future delivery plans across the nine participating farms are presented in the table below, providing a clear visual overview of planned actions set against established targets. Many of the interventions that land managers are seeking to undertake have the potential to make a meaningful contribution to those targets. Given that the majority of land managers have been or are currently enrolled in a Higher-Level Stewardship (HLS) agreement, and manage their land under one or more regulatory frameworks – including Sites of Special Scientific Interest (SSSIs), Special Areas of Conservation (SACs), and Special Protection Areas (SPAs) – many of their stated future delivery plans tend to align closely with existing practices, frequently representing an expansion or deepening of work already undertaken on their land. Despite this, several participants had fairly ambitious plans, often involving taking new actions and altering their management practices, e.g. introduction of cattle grazing.

Table 3 shows the total area size of priority habitat across the nine farms, alongside the total area size to be either enhanced or created. Given all holdings make up a total of around 12,000 hectares, the vast majority of the land (9108.5ha) falls within the ‘priority habitat’ category. The proportion of new land to be brought under new environmental land management represents 22% of the total area size of priority habitat.

Table 3: Areas to be protected or restored

Priority habitat	Total area size across all farms	Total area to be created/enhanced
<i>Upland heathland</i>	5145.5ha	506ha
<i>Blanket bog</i>	3577.5ha	1070.5ha
<i>Upland oak woodland</i>	116.5ha	141.25ha
<i>Purple moor grass and rush pasture</i>	69.75ha	N/A
<i>Upland flushes, fens and swamps</i>	43ha	N/A

<i>Wet heathland with cross-leaved heath, upland (H4010)</i>	35ha	22.5ha
<i>Wood pasture and parkland</i>	34ha	154.25ha
<i>Lowland dry acid grassland</i>	32ha	21ha
<i>Lowland hay meadows</i>	19.75ha	78.05ha
<i>Lowland heathland</i>	15ha	N/A
<i>Good quality semi-improved grassland</i>	15ha	N/A
<i>Mixed scrub</i>	2.5ha	20ha
<i>Upland birch woodland/broadleaved</i>	1.25ha	21ha
<i>Scot's Pine woodland</i>	1ha	
<i>Wet woodland</i>	0.75ha	1ha
<i>Wetland (scrapes)</i>	-	11.55ha
<i>Upland hay meadows</i>	-	7ha
Total	9108.5ha	2054.1ha

The participating sheep farmers demonstrated a general willingness to consider a broad range of interventions, including woodland creation and the establishment of species-rich meadows. This openness may reflect both a long-standing engagement with agri-environment schemes and an appreciation of the financial contribution that such schemes make to the viability of their farm businesses.

All moorland owners expressed willingness to pursue peatland restoration, and many had already made some progress in this area. However, some concerns were raised regarding the effectiveness of certain interventions, and as a result, moorland owners indicated a desire to retain a degree of control and oversight over the precise nature and implementation of restoration activities on their land.

An overview of the targets and plans can be found below. Please note that the 'plans' column was not ordered to reflect the order in which the targets are listed in the other column.

Table 4: Targets and future delivery plans

	Targets	Plans
Habitat creation & restoration	Create or restore 250,000 ha of a range of wildlife-rich habitat by 2030 outside of protected sites and 500,000 ha by 2042	Enhancing lowland hay meadows to increase species richness
	Maintain and enhance priority habitats including species-rich grasslands, clough woodlands, wet woodland, acid grassland and riparian zones	Wetland creation (scrapes, ponds, open water areas on moorland etc.) for waders, amphibians, invertebrates

	Restore or improve habitats on SSSIs, with 50 percent on track by 2028.	Introduce cattle grazing to diversify vegetation, support wading birds, and enhance species poor moorland
	Increase tree and woodland cover, including field corners, cloughs, extensions of existing woodlands, shelterbelts and wood pasture by 0.33% (net increase = 43,000ha)	Expand woodland and scrub for livestock/game shelter
	Restore and plant more hedgerows—48,000km by 2037 - 72,400km by 2050	Peatland restoration: Re-vegetate bare peat, block gullies with turf dams, and re-profile slopes
	Double the number of farms providing sufficient year-round resources for farm wildlife compared with 2025	Restore mixed scrub: Introduce berry-bearing species (rowan, hawthorn, bird cherry) in gorse/bracken-dominated areas
		Stream enhancement to boost salmon population and aquatic biodiversity
Targets		
Water, soil health, & flood management	Reduce agricultural nitrogen, phosphorus and sediment pollution by 12 percent by 2030 and 40 percent by 2038 and by 18 percent in catchments containing protected sites in unfavourable condition due to pollution	Plans Expand the use of deep-rooting herbal leys and over-seed legumes to fix nitrogen and build soil organic matter
	Improve the environmental condition of rivers, streams, ponds and lakes to good ecological status	Low input farming to diffuse pollution risks
	Create habitats such as buffer strips and riparian corridors	Natural flood management through leaky/woody debris dams in woodlands to reduce downstream flood risk or turf dams on moorland
	Deliver natural flood management interventions	
	Bring 40 percent of agricultural soils into sustainable management by 2028 and 60% by 2030	
Targets		
Peatlands	Restore 280,000ha of peatland in England by 2050 by reducing erosion, blocking grips and gullies and encouraging dynamic peat-	Plans Peatland restoration (gully blocking, reprofiling, revegetation, e.g. sphagnum and woodland wherever suitable) for carbon storage, water retention, erosion

	forming vegetation communities	reduction and lower downstream sediment
	Reduced wildfire risk	Develop a wildfire risk management plan to create firebreaks, e.g. cutting, encourage less flammable vegetation near roads/tracks, rewet peatland, and ensure water sources for firefighting
Targets		Plans
Climate & wildfire resilience	England to reach net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050	Enhance carbon sequestration on peatland through active peat formation and water storage
	Protected Landscapes to restore 130,000 ha of peat by 2050 and increase the tree canopy area by 3 percent	Slow water flow by creating dams
	Increase climate resilience through adaption and positive action to reverse damage from climate change to nature, biodiversity, cultural heritage	Wetland creation on in-bye grassland to support wildlife during dry springs and provide drinking water
Targets		Plans
Species recovery	Halt the decline of in species abundance by 2030	Support wading birds, merlins, and short-eared owls by creating scrapes and ponds on in-bye land, diversifying vegetation structure, controlling predators, rewetting moorland, enhancing wetland plants, refining moorland grazing, avoiding moorland works during breeding season
	Restore and manage moorland to support increased breeding populations of Merlin, Golden Plover and Short-eared Owl	Support flycatchers, redstarts, tree pipits, woodcocks, cuckoos through woodland creation
		Support invertebrates through the creation of wetlands and diversification of vegetation.

Future delivery ambitions exhibited notable variation across the holdings involved in the study. While some land managers demonstrated a clear willingness to expand their efforts, others were more cautious in their commitments. This disparity was further complicated by the intricate occupancy structures that characterise land management in England. Specifically, tenant sheep farmers and their landlords at times held divergent levels of ambition regarding nature recovery and climate resilience, reflecting the complexities inherent in multi-stakeholder land management systems.

5. REVIEW OF PARTICIPANTS' EXPERIENCES

5.1. Motivations for participating in the project

Participating land managers collectively regard the project as an important initial phase in fostering broader, landscape-scale collaboration aimed at nature recovery and climate resilience, including initiatives like the higher-tier Landscape Recovery agri-environment scheme (LRS). For sheep farmers, access to subsidised, large-scale collaborative efforts is considered vital to sustaining their businesses. One land manager identified the primary reason for engaging in a higher-tier scheme such as the LRS as 'financial to start with because as a hill farm now, without support, not just our business but a lot more farming businesses on the hill will not be viable' (Land Manager 1). This viewpoint is partially reflected by another sheep farmer, who emphasised the importance of 'making sure that we get a fair deal' (Land Manager 3) within the shifting landscape of agricultural subsidies.

A further significant motivation, observed among both sheep farmers and grouse moor managers, is the desire for greater control, which a farmer-centred approach can help achieve. One land manager expressed this perspective clearly:

'I believe that land management should really be better left and controlled by the people on the ground rather than people sitting behind desks in some regional NGO office. And this felt like a way of trying to take back some control from the agencies who we don't think serve us very well and deliver the environmental goods at a lower cost to society.' (Land Manager 7)

As a result, the project – and the potential Landscape Recovery Scheme application it may lead to – is perceived by participating land managers as 'an opportunity for [them] to be in control of what is going up on the land' (Land Manager 3), while also ensuring the long-term sustainability of hill farming enterprises.

5.2. Demands for outcome-based programmes

The prescriptive nature of current agri-environment schemes and broader environmental policies was a recurring theme among participating land managers. This prescriptiveness appears to contribute significantly to their perception of limited agency or control in implementing nature recovery and climate resilience measures. In contrast, land managers expressed a strong preference for a farmer-centred approach, emphasising outcome-based frameworks that allow for greater autonomy in decision-making. As articulated by one land manager:

'If they say you know you need X number of birds, they shouldn't tell us how to achieve that, they should measure it on the success of the outcomes. And the same goes for different species of grassland or moorland vegetation.' (Land Manager 4)

Several rationales underpin this demand for control through an outcome-based approach to environmental land management. A primary motivation is the deep personal and historical connection land managers have with their land, often spanning generations of family stewardship. This connection fosters an expectation of managerial autonomy. Additionally, land managers argue that their intimate, daily knowledge of the land positions them uniquely to determine which actions are effective and which are not. This perspective is illustrated in the following interview excerpt:

‘We want to be more in control of introducing that nature that they wanted because we can see that we, as practical farmers and landowners, can see the wrongs in what’s happening. And we don’t think, well, we’ll do something and, oh, it’s wrong, we want paying, well we’ll put it right again.’ (Land Manager 3)

Embedded within this call for greater control is the belief that land managers are not only more likely to ensure actions achieve the desired outcomes but can also do so ‘very quickly and very economically’ (Land Manager 3). They contend that their localised expertise and capacity for direct observation enable them to implement measures efficiently. This sentiment is further echoed by one participant, who asserted that the project and the opportunity to develop a Landscape Recovery Scheme (LRS) bid would help recognise the ‘expertise’ they claim has been ‘ignored’ in environmental land management to date (Land Manager 7). Notably, this preference for payment-by-results programs is also supported by a key local stakeholder, who remarked that ‘a proposal for payment by results [...] would have been a really good thing.’ (Stakeholder 1)

While the project itself may not have directly resulted in the formulation of landscape-scale outcomes or a clear proposal for a collaborative, outcome-based programme, the groundwork laid during its implementation could inform and facilitate future initiatives of this nature.

5.3. Assessing the degree of ambition

At the interviews, land managers and stakeholders were asked to reflect on the aspirations outlined in individual farm plans. Many land managers emphasised that they are already implementing significant measures for nature recovery and climate resilience. For instance, one participant stated ‘we are already meeting a lot of these targets.’ (Land Manager 1)

Another highlighted the risks of certain approaches, cautioning against assumptions that favour no intervention or no grazing, due to the ‘danger of catastrophic wildfires’ (Land Manager 4). Despite these ongoing efforts, there was broad acknowledgment among participants that adaptations in land management practices are necessary. A grouse moor manager noted ‘we might have to adapt a bit’ (Land Manager 2). Another land manager elaborated on the potential scope of these changes:

‘I think in certain respects we’ll be changing it and in other respects we’ll be carrying on and in other respects maybe we’ll be tweaking it slightly.’ (Land Manager 5)

This recognition of the need for change extended across different land uses. For example, sheep farmers expressed willingness to introduce cattle grazing, while a grouse moor manager also considered this option:

‘We haven’t got any cattle at the moment but we discussed starting a small, a relatively modest cattle number to vary the grazing on certain areas.’ (Land Manager 5)

However, the level of ambition varied significantly across holdings. Some land managers were more open to measures such as tree planting, while others were more cautious. This variation led a local stakeholder to suggest that successful practices on one holding could serve as a ‘case study’ or model for others (Stakeholder 1).

Stakeholders emphasised that successful applications for LRS would require highly ambitious targets and a demonstrable commitment to changing current land management practices. This could involve not only creating habitats for species like waders on moorland but also, critically,

on in-bye land, where these species thrive. Achieving this would necessitate adjustments to grazing patterns to support their survival. However, it remained unclear to this stakeholder whether participating land managers were prepared to adopt such changes.

While ambition levels differed among land managers – and many asserted they are already contributing significantly to nature recovery and climate resilience – there was consensus that some degree of change in management practices is essential to meet key local environmental objectives. Both the project consultant and stakeholders suggested that collaborative planning, such as bringing land managers together to share ambitions and strategies, could be the most effective approach to achieving the goals of LRS.

5.4. Assessing the process

To enhance the effectiveness of the farmer-led process for future applications – both within the Peak District and in other regions – interview questions collected the view of land managers, the consultant, and local stakeholders on various aspects of the initiative.

Land managers consistently praised the consultant's role, emphasising both the facilitation of the process and the quality of the resulting farm plans. As one land manager noted:

'I think it was all professionally done, we discussed all the various issues on several occasions and we came up with a vision for the future which we would be happy to implement given the right backing from the government agencies.' (Land Manager 5)

A notable advantage was the pre-existing relationship between the land managers and the consultant. Familiarity and trust were cited as critical factors in maximising the limited time available. The individual farm plans were particularly well-received for their clarity, conciseness, and accurate reflection of both baseline and future delivery intentions. While feedback on the farmer checklist was limited – with few land managers recalling its contents – those who did engage with it found it useful and accessible. Additionally, land managers who attended the final group meeting responded positively to the GWCT representative's presentation, which they felt effectively captured their ongoing work and level of ambition.

Despite the overall success, several suggestions for refinement were proposed by the consultant and local stakeholders, particularly in alignment with the expectations of LRS. One key recommendation was to allocate time for at least one meeting involving only the participating land managers and the facilitator/consultant. Such a session would foster greater collaboration and enable land managers to explore opportunities for landscape-scale outcomes, such as envisioning how 'woodlands join up across holdings' (Stakeholder 1) However, the short duration of the project posed challenges in organising such a meeting, leaving uncertainty about whether the required level of collaboration for LRS was fully achieved.

Stakeholder 1 also suggested incorporating site visits, allowing land managers to observe practices on each other's holdings. This approach could raise ambition and strengthen collaborative efforts. The consultant recommended conducting the project during a season more conducive to on-site exploration, particularly for holdings less familiar to the consultant. While progress was made through discussions, a more robust assessment of baseline and future delivery plans could have been achieved through 'going around the farm' (Consultant).

Another suggestion by the same stakeholder emphasised the need for better preparation for collaboration at the project's outset. Activities such as reviewing high-quality management

practices, visiting each other's holdings, and dedicating a day to discussing collaboration could have elevated land managers' ambitions. This approach would also allow the consultant to adopt a more proactive role in steering the project, such as demonstrating the potential outcomes of specific actions or management strategies.

Several suggestions were also made about the group meetings. An important suggestion was to make sure that future group meetings of this kind involved all land managers and more time for stakeholders to discuss the issues at stake. Issues were also raised regarding the extrapolation of individual farm plans' aspirations to the entire PEF membership. More could have instead been done to narrate what those plans might mean for landscape-scale collaboration. Another important point was made about ensuring that historical differences between different parties are parked and discussions offer a constructive space for collaboration.

Finally, the consultant highlighted the need for a clearer assignment of responsibilities from the beginning, given the project's short-term nature. Some ambiguity persisted regarding task allocation, which could be addressed in future iterations.

5.5. Conclusion: building on the momentum

Many involved in the project acknowledged that this was a new and innovative initiative, recognising that there is much to learn from the experience – an outcome that holds significant value in itself. The process provided a unique opportunity to test approaches, gather insights, and refine methods for future applications, not only within the Peak District but also in similar contexts elsewhere.

Beyond viewing the project as a learning experience, it was also described as a 'valuable first step towards thinking about what could happen on participating land managers' holdings' (Stakeholder 1). Land managers themselves expressed a strong desire to build on the momentum generated by the project, emphasising their eagerness to identify short- and medium-term opportunities for collaboration. This proactive approach is intended to lay the groundwork for a more ambitious and cohesive application under the longer-term LRS. One land manager proposed resuming discussions as early as May 2026, once the demands of the lambing season have eased, to maintain this forward momentum. Such discussions could include working out how the participating land managers could take the work undertaken as part of this project forward and begin to prioritise areas for collaboration in preparation for an LRS application. In response to interview questions around the next steps and expectations associated with LRS, stakeholders provided some possible themes for discussion and insights into what a successful LRS application might look like. Those are as follows:

- The core and distinctive landscape in the Dark Peak is peatland.
- A suggestion was made to make peatland restoration a centrepiece of the application.
- Stakeholder 2 highlighted that a key strength of the Environmentally Sensitive Areas (ESA) schemes was their inclusive approach: each agreement engages all parties with a vested interest in land management – farmers, gamekeepers, and landowners. LRS offers these stakeholders an opportunity to work together to conserve and restore the truly special area they have helped shape over time.
- Land managers might consider meeting a range of collaboratively identified outcomes after 25 years.

- Applications might, for example, include a demonstrable commitment to rewetting moorland areas or a demonstrable commitment to bold woodland creation where trees do not have to compete with peat.
- How land managers achieve those outcomes will be their decision and responsibility, but a demonstrable commitment to such outcomes will be key to securing a successful LRS application.
- Meeting those outcomes might require changes in grazing patterns alongside the creation of scrapes or enforcing predator control alongside the creation of woodland.

Given the experimental nature of the project, it was inevitable that challenges would arise, particularly in aligning the initiative with the diverse expectations of all parties involved. However, the interviews conducted at the conclusion of the project revealed a shared sense of optimism. Participants recognised that the work undertaken had already begun to yield tangible opportunities – opportunities that do not need to wait for the formal application to the LRS. Many of these possibilities can be pursued in the medium and even short term.

One particularly promising suggestion, put forward by a local stakeholder and supported by land managers, was to develop a collaborative payment-by-result proposal at a landscape scale. Such an initiative would not only capitalise on the current momentum and address the varied needs of those involved but would also serve as a constructive stepping stone toward a future Landscape Recovery Scheme application. By fostering collaboration and demonstrating early successes, this approach could strengthen the case for broader, long-term environmental and agricultural improvements.

More concretely, then, the next steps could involve the following:

- **As soon as possible:** liaise with relevant stakeholders, especially the Peak District National Park, to explore options for short-term funding opportunities and for a payment-by-result proposal based.
- **May/June:** meeting between land managers to discuss possible areas of collaboration for short-term funding opportunities and payment-by-result proposal emerging from the individual farm plans.
- **After May/June meeting:** consider inviting other geographically contiguous PEF members to collaborate on broad plans devised at the meeting.

6. FARMER-LED APPROACH TOOLKIT

The experimental nature of this project provided a valuable opportunity to learn and understand how future farmer-centred approaches – particularly those aimed at applying for higher-tier schemes like the Landscape Recovery Scheme (LRS) – could replicate and refine this model to enhance the likelihood of a successful application. In what follows are a selection of replicable tools suggested for a farmer-centred approach drawing on the lessons learned for this FiPL-funded project and aimed at preparing its participants for a collaborative landscape recovery programme.

Role of the consultant/facilitator

- The involvement of a trusted consultant to facilitate the farmer-led process is widely regarded as essential by land managers.
- Their role includes supporting land managers in designing environmental objectives, such as developing the *Farmer Checklist* and creating individual farm plans.
- A proactive (steering) role in suggesting environmental objectives closely aligned with LRS requirements could further maximise success during the application stage.

Farmer checklist

- Conduct a (desk-based) scoping study to identify relevant national, regional, and local environmental targets for the selected landscape recovery area.
- Distill these targets into a concise, accessible document to share with participating land managers before the first group meeting and farm visits.
- Highlight opportunities for cross-holding collaboration.

Start-of-process meeting with land managers and stakeholders

- Focus on discussing the *Farmer Checklist* targets and local stakeholder expectations, particularly those related to LRS.
- Ensure all participating land managers are invited and attend the group meeting.
- Agree on key areas of collaboration and desired outcomes.

Exploring ambitious landscape recovery practices

- Use case studies to examine specific conservation practices, such as woodland creation or rewetting.
- Organise visits for land managers to holdings where these practices are already in place.
- Encourage land managers to visit each other's holdings to observe current practices and inspire further collaboration.

Follow-up meeting between land managers

- Build on the initial group meeting and exploration of ambitious recovery practices.
- Facilitated by the consultant, who presents previously discussed outcomes and areas of collaboration while chairing the meeting.
- Focus on determining actionable steps to achieve the identified outcomes and collaborative goals.

Individual farm plans

- Based on the *Farmer Checklist* and farm visits involving the relevant land manager and project consultant.

- Each plan should include: an overview of the farm (characteristics, history of participation in agri-environment schemes, and existing environmental assets), the stated aspirations of farmers and landowners, the alignment with national, regional, and local environmental priorities and targets, and identified opportunities for environmental enhancement.
- Visualise the holding using tools like LandApp and through on-site visits.
- Schedule farm visits outside of winter months to allow for better on-the-ground assessment.
- Record aspirations in real time using notes and/or LandApp.
- The consultant should guide aspirations toward the outcomes and collaborative areas discussed in previous meetings.
- In cases of complex occupancy structures, ensure all relevant stakeholders are engaged.

End-of-process group meeting with land managers and stakeholders

- Focus on gathering feedback on the farm plans from both land managers and local stakeholders.
- Provide feedback with the LRS application in mind, emphasising elements critical for a successful bid.
- Identify potential next steps in the short, medium, and long term.
- Ensure land managers and stakeholders have equal opportunities to contribute to the discussion.

7. APPENDIX

Farmer Checklist – Delivering Increased Biodiversity and Climate Resilience

England's environmental policy sets clear goals for improving nature, water, soil and climate resilience through a range of policy documents including the Environmental Improvement Plan, the Peak District National Park Management Plan and the Protected Landscapes Targets and Outcomes Framework.

Farmers and land managers are central to achieving these targets and providing the ecosystem services associated with them as they require delivery on farmland, alongside the production of high quality food.

Below are the key areas where your farm actions make the biggest contribution.

1. Nature Recovery and Habitats

- Create or restore **250,000 ha** of a range of **wildlife-rich habitat by 2030** outside of protected sites and **500,000 ha by 2042**
- Maintain and enhance **priority habitats** including species-rich grasslands, clough woodlands, wet woodland, acid grassland and riparian zones.
- Restore or improve habitats on **SSSIs**, with **50 percent on track by 2028**.
- Increase **tree and woodland cover**, including field corners, cloughs, extensions of existing woodlands, shelterbelts and wood pasture by 0.33% (net increase = 43,000ha)
- Restore and plant **more hedgerows**—48,000km by 2037 - 72,400km by 2050
- **Double the number of farms** providing sufficient year-round resources for farm wildlife compared with 2025

What can you do on your farm:

- Woodland creation
- Hedgerow planting
- Grassland creation, restoration, enhancement and management
- Scrub and wood pasture creation and management

2. Clean and Plentiful Water

- Reduce **agricultural nitrogen, phosphorus and sediment pollution** by 12 percent by 2030 and 40 percent by 2038 and by 18 percent in catchments containing protected sites in unfavourable condition due to pollution
- Improve the environmental condition of rivers, streams, ponds and lakes to **good ecological status**
- Create habitats such as buffer strips and riparian corridors
- Deliver natural flood management interventions

What can you do on your farm?

- Fencing off sensitive open water features, farm infrastructure – clean and dirty water separation and NFM interventions
 - Consider land use and management changes which will help to prevent poaching, soil erosion and water run off
-

3. Healthy, Sustainable Soils

- Bring **40 percent of agricultural soils into sustainable management by 2028** and **60% by 2030**.

What can you do on your farm?

- Complete a soil assessment and soil management plan
- Establish multi-species leys on improved grassland currently in a monoculture
- Consider changes to grazing management such as adopting rotational or paddock grazing to reduce compaction and increase soil organic matter levels

4. Climate Mitigation and Resilience

- England to reach **net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050**.
- Protected Landscapes to **restore 130,000 ha of peat by 2050** and increase the tree canopy area by 3 percent
- **Increase climate resilience** through adaptation and positive action to reverse damage from climate change to nature, biodiversity, cultural heritage

What can you do on your farm?

- Peatland restoration
- More wet habitats – grassland, woodland, scrapes, ponds and pools
- Trees on farmland - wood pasture, agroforestry, shelterbelts and copses
- Climate-resilient grazing systems

5. Peatlands

- **Restore 280,000ha of peatland in England by 2050** by reducing erosion, blocking grips and gullies and encouraging dynamic peat-forming vegetation communities
- Reduced wildfire risk

What can you do on your farm?

- Restore peatlands by restoring hydrological intactness
- Implement an adaptive grazing regime which creates structural diversity within heathland vegetation and discourages dominance by *Molinia*

6. Species recovery

- **Halt the decline of in species abundance by 2030** by taking targeted action
- Restore and manage moorland to provide suitable habitat and conditions to support increased breeding populations of **Merlin, Golden Plover and Short-eared Owl**

What can you do on your farm?

- Implement suitable grazing regimes to create a varied range of habitat for breeding, feeding and for prey species
- Effective, legal predation control

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RENEWING Biodiversity through a people-in-nature-approach

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